

Foresight for Opportunity Crop Development

Summary

This brief presents a strategic framework for integrating opportunity crops into African food systems through foresight-driven planning and multi-stakeholder collaboration. Drawing on pilot workshops in Nigeria, Kenya, and Zambia conducted by the Power of Diversity Funding Facility with support from Foresight4Food, the paper demonstrates how combining food systems analysis with foresight methodologies enables inclusive decision-making for the prioritization and development of opportunity crops. Traditional agricultural planning based on historical data can marginalize opportunity crops despite their potential to address nutrition insecurity, climate vulnerability and rural livelihoods. A forward-looking approach that anticipates future scenarios – climate shifts, demographic transitions, dietary changes – leads to proactive rather than reactive crop development strategies.

1. Introduction: The Imperative for Crop Diversification

Global food systems face converging challenges due to climate change, environmental degradation, biodiversity loss and persistent food insecurity. A critical, and urgent, response strategy is diversification of the crop menu beyond dominant staple crops, including through the inclusion of crops that are often referred to as neglected and underutilized species, orphan crops, minor crops, or forgotten foods. Despite being marginalised today, they have substantial potential for contributing to future food systems. These opportunity crops – resilient, nutritious, traditionally cultivated species – offer pathways to strengthen sustainability and resilience while honouring diverse culinary traditions. The 2025

EAT-Lancet 2.0 report reinforces the conclusions of numerous previous studies highlighting the imperative of shifting to more nutritious, diverse and sustainable diets for human health and environmental protection.

Opportunity crops remain marginalized in research, breeding and conservation efforts. This means their potential remains largely untapped, while their genetic diversity faces ongoing erosion. Conserving this diversity, including through genebanks, is critical – it safeguards the biological foundations needed to adapt to evolving climate, nutrition and market demands. However, conservation is not enough.

Effective action must span from seed to plate, embedding opportunity crops within broader ecosystems of innovation, policy and market development. A food systems perspective provides a tool for understanding the complex relationships at play.

Foresight strengthens this systems perspective by integrating uncertainty and disruptive change into strategic decision-making. Unlike forecasting, foresight explores alternative futures through horizon scanning, visioning and scenario analysis – helping stakeholders anticipate future pressures, shocks and opportunities and assess pathways toward desirable futures. Foresight can support conservation strategies and opportunity crop development to align with the long-term needs of creating more resilient and healthy food systems. The Foresight4Food Framework emphasises

the integration of participatory stakeholder engagement with the use of good evidence and quantitative data and modelling.

The Power of Diversity Funding Facility (Funding Facility), managed by the Global Crop Diversity Trust, supports conservation and use of opportunity crops to enhance food security, climate resilience and rural livelihoods across Africa, Asia, the Pacific, Latin America and the Caribbean. This brief synthesizes lessons from pilot Funding Facility stakeholder workshops in Nigeria, Zambia and Kenya, demonstrating how food systems and foresight approaches can guide decision-making for prioritisation of opportunity crops for conservation and development. Further sections outline other cases of application of foresight methodologies to opportunity crop conservation and use.

2. A Participatory, Systems and Foresight Approach to Opportunity Crop Development

2.1 Foresight for opportunity crop prioritization

The Funding Facility piloted a food systems (see Figure 1) and future-oriented methodology through two-day workshops with 40-50 diverse stakeholders per country – including farmers, genebank managers, researchers, breeders, private sector, civil society, consumer representatives and policymakers. The workshops integrated elements of the Foresight4Food Foresight for Food Systems Change Framework (see Figure 2). The process involved the following steps.

Crop prioritization (initial): A list of 48 crops (cereals, roots & tubers, fruits, vegetables, legumes, nuts, seeds & oilseeds) was developed based on earlier research under the Vision for Adapted Crops and Soils and other secondary data and validated by national partners. Criteria considered included resilience to climate change, potential contributions to food and nutrition security and sustainable livelihoods, as well as the status of conservation.

Foresight and systems mapping: Participants developed a shared understanding of national food systems, including production, trade, consumption, governance and preliminary gender and conflict analyses. This framing revealed how social, economic and environmental factors shape crop opportunities and how system constraints influence the potential adoption and impact of opportunity crops. Through “data walks”, participants engaged with evidence on drivers of change, including demographic shifts, climate change, nutrition needs and gender dynamics, discussing their implications for different opportunity crops. Small group discussions clustered insights into key themes, building a collective understanding of how different crops could contribute to the future of food security, livelihoods, climate resilience, and environmental sustainability.

Crop prioritization (refined): A four-round process involved: (1) validation of opportunity crops against prioritization criteria per crop category (cereals, roots and tuber, nuts and oil crops, legumes, fruits, vegetables); (2) prioritization based

on climate adaptability, nutritional value, cultural acceptance and market potential in each category; (3) rating on 1-3 scale all crops prioritized in the previous step; and (4) final pairwise ranking by stakeholder groups to arrive at the final selection of opportunity crops.

Stakeholder mapping for selected crops:

Groups identified key actors across domains, specified roles and connections and highlighted stakeholders that are both high-interest and high-influence in relation to the value chains of the selected crops for ongoing engagement.

Rich pictures: To develop a deeper understanding of the factors enabling or constraining adoption, participatory visual maps of the value chains for the selected crops were developed. This process looked at each crop in relation to the wider food system, helping to identify future challenges and topics requiring further analysis, as well as surfacing critical policy, political economy and power dynamic issues.

Figure 1. Food systems model used to help workshop participants explore and understand how opportunity crops fit within wider food systems dynamics.

Figure 2. The Foresight4Food Framework of Foresight for Food Systems Change.

The workshops led to a prioritisation of opportunity crops for each country:

- Nigeria: Fonio and pigeon pea
- Zambia: Sorghum and cowpea
- Kenya: Finger millet and amaranth

Participants praised the methodology for enabling collaborative exploration of trade-offs and aligning diverse priorities within a holistic perspective which included conservation, livelihoods, nutrition and health objectives.

The crop selections clearly reflected potential for both climate adaptation and nutritional benefits. The process was participatory, democratic and context-specific to the Funding Facility's

implementation scope. Alongside enabling a future-oriented and rigorous selection process, the methodology gave all stakeholders a deeper understanding of the value chain challenges that may be faced in the development of the different crops. The integration of additional evidence on key crop characteristics and conservation status could be strengthened in future use of the methodology.

The experience of integrating foresight and systems approaches into the opportunity crop selection process illustrates the potential benefits of a wider application and institutionalisation of foresight for all aspects of crop diversification. These are described in the following sections.

Workshop participants discussing the prioritization of opportunity crops in Nigeria.

Workshop participant presenting stakeholder influence matrix in Zambia.

Workshop participants discussing food systems trends in Nigeria.

Workshop participants developing "rich pictures" of interactions of actors in a prioritized value chain in Nigeria.

2.2 Foresight for genebanks conserving opportunity crops

Genebanks around the world safeguard millions of crop accessions that underpin future global food security, but they face resource constraints requiring strategic prioritization. Foresight inverts reactive conservation by starting with future scenarios and working backward to identify which genetic resources may be most valuable for particular purposes.

Climate scenarios: help to identify critical traits to ensure food systems resilience – disease resistance, drought and heat tolerance, flood resilience. This enables prioritization of wild relatives and landraces potentially containing adaptive traits.

Nutrition scenarios: enable understanding of future nutrition needs caused by aging populations, urbanization, increased micronutrient awareness and shifting markets. This understanding can enable prioritizing nutrient-dense landraces and neglected species.

Data integration: foresight and systems approaches can support genebanks to integrate and make sense of a wider range of data sources, including passport data, phenotypic characterization, genomic information and geographic data. A foresight framework helps to make use of climate models, crop distribution databases, predictive analytics and machine learning to improve future-oriented decision-making.

2.3 Foresight for development of opportunity crop value chains

Opportunity crop value chains are often characterized by high transaction costs and inefficiencies. Market potentials are often unused and opportunities for sustainable livelihoods and nutrition remain unused. Foresight enables proactive investment by anticipating market shifts, technological breakthroughs and consumer trends. Participatory foresight processes can support all value chain actors, including producers, traders, processors and retailers to better understand future opportunities and better coordinate to overcome value chain constraints.

Market analysis of emerging consumer trends (e.g. plant-based proteins, functional foods, climate-resilient ingredients) and demographic shifts (e.g. urbanisation, middle-class growth) is critical for positioning opportunity crops. Foresight supports spotting longer-term trends and developing scenarios for different market conditions. This can in turn help to ensure that opportunity crop development is realistically aligned with market dynamics.

Seed systems are a foundation for the development of opportunity crops. Foresight enables breeding programs to be more anticipatory and adaptive to potential future market demands. The foresight process can bring researchers, plant breeders and private sector seed companies together to align their strategies in support of an effective seed system.

Climate change will increasingly impact opportunity crop value chains through weather extremes, pest and disease outbreaks, and market fluctuations. Foresight enables such potential shocks to be better understood and mitigation mechanisms to be put in place, e.g. micro-insurance, weather forecasting, early warning systems and improved storage. Foresight also enables the case for opportunity crops to be more effectively made in appropriate fora.

Policy shifts, related to subsidies, trade agreements, nutrition programmes, social protection, school feeding and quality and safety standards, all impact opportunity crop development. Foresight enables emerging policy directions to be identified and responded to, and for advocates of opportunity crops to better engage in policy dialogue.

Technology developments such as digital financial services, blockchain tracking and tracing, biofortification, e-commerce and AI information services could potentially all contribute to the development of opportunity crop value chains. Technology horizon scanning can help to ensure the risks and opportunities of emerging technologies are factored into opportunity crop development.

2.4 Foresight for integrating opportunity crops into policy frameworks

Opportunity crops remain marginalized in many national policies despite their potential. Traditional policymaking relies on historical data, which may inadvertently reinforce dominant staple crops by reflecting historical priorities that no longer align with contemporary challenges. Foresight enables anticipatory approaches to agriculture and food related policies, opening up space for consideration of the potential positive impact of opportunity crops.

Agricultural policy: can be supported by scenario planning that models climate impacts on staple crop production. This can reveal where opportunity crops offer comparative advantages, providing rationale for reallocating research funding, extension services and subsidies now rather than waiting for crises. Similarly, horizon scanning can identify emerging pest and disease pressures on major crops, flagging opportunity crops with natural resistance as strategic alternatives warranting investment.

Nutrition policy: requires demographic and epidemiological foresight to reveal evolving challenges. Scenario analysis demonstrates how nutritionally dense opportunity crops can address micronutrient gaps cost-effectively, supporting integration into school feeding, maternal nutrition and public procurement.

Trade policy: can be strengthened through foresight analysis of global commodity markets, climate impacts on exporters and geopolitical risks, helping to anticipate import vulnerabilities and creating the strategic rationale for import substitution by using opportunity crops. Regional frameworks like the African Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA) can be leveraged more strategically through foresight analysis to support the necessary harmonized standards, phytosanitary protocols and trade facilitation measures for opportunity crops.

Policy incentives: can be reformed through foresight by clarifying beneficiaries, identifying barriers, and anticipating unintended consequences – enabling redesign of subsidies, research funding, market development programs, and extension services.

3. Recommendations

The experience of the pilot workshops on opportunity crop selection and the wider outlook outlined above lead to the following recommendations for strengthening the use of foresight and food systems analysis.

1. Institutionalize foresight-driven planning:

Integrate foresight, scenario planning and horizon scanning into national policy and planning processes, including National Food Systems Transformation Pathways, National Adaptation Plans (NAPs), Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs), and National Biodiversity Strategies and Action Plans (NBSAPs) and ensure crop diversity is part of the analysis. Build and refresh foresight capacity across policy makers, researchers and extension services. Ensure foresight methods and data explicitly include assessment of women and youth, marginalised groups, smallholder farmers and indigenous communities.

2. Realign public investment for future-proof diversification:

Use foresight insights to help reallocate subsidies, research funding, and extension resources toward enhanced use of opportunity crops. This may include the integration of opportunity crop products into school feeding, maternal health programs and food aid.

3. Underpin genetic resource conservation with foresight analysis:

Prioritize conservation of genetic resources valuable under multiple future scenarios—drought tolerance, heat resistance, flooding and nutritional density. Strengthen digital platforms integrating agronomic and genomic data with climate and market simulation models. Deploy machine learning to help identify high-value uncharacterized accessions.

4. Use foresight-oriented multi-stakeholder processes at multiple scales to underpin innovation:

Establish participatory platforms uniting genebank managers, farmers, processors, nutritionists and policymakers to explore scenarios and coordinate investments. Use scenario analysis to help strengthen regional coordination and cooperation through ECOWAS, SADC and EAC to harmonize research, seed systems and trade facilitation that is supportive of opportunity crops.

5. Enable strategic private sector engagement:

Use foresight to help identify longer-term market and investment opportunities for opportunity crops (understanding consumer trends and market drivers) and structure public-private partnerships and blended finance mechanisms to support transition towards more resilient agrifood systems. Adopt foresight tools to understand how value chains can be supported through public investment for early-stage development (germplasm, agronomy, seed systems) and private sector for processing and distribution as markets mature.

6. Integrate data-driven foresight tools with processes of multi-stakeholder consultations:

Optimise the potential of foresight and scenarios for supporting genebanks and opportunity crop development by effective integration of qualitative and quantitative foresight approaches.

4. Conclusion

The future of African food systems will be shaped by climate change, urbanization, demographic shifts and evolving trade relations. Opportunity crops can serve as strategic levers for transformation – but only if conservation, development, and policy frameworks not only react to, but also anticipate these dynamics. The Funding Facility's pilot workshops demonstrate that combining food systems analysis with participatory foresight can support robust, inclusive decision-making that aligns diverse stakeholder priorities while preparing for multiple plausible futures. Institutionalizing these approaches across genebanks, value chains and policy processes can help realize the full potential of crop diversity to build resilient, sustainable and just food systems.

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